

Deliverable D4.2 Updated ELIXIR Long-term Sustainability Plan

Project Title (Grant agreement no.):	ELIXIR-CONVERGE: Connect and align ELIXIR Nodes to deliver sustainable FAIR life-science data management services (871075)		
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Deliverable Lead Beneficiary:	1 - ELIXIR Hub		
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Partner(s) contributing to this deliverable:	ELIXIR Hub		
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Reviewers:	ELIXIR-CONVERGE Management Board (MB) members.		

Log of changes

DATE	Mvm	Who	Description
31/07/2022	0v1	Andrew Smith, Corinne Martin (ELIXIR Hub)	Initial version
25/5/2023	0v2	Andrew Smith (ELIXIR Hub)	Sent to PMU after incorporating internal WP feedback
19/05/2023	0v3	Juan Arenas (ELIXIR Hub)	Circulated to the MB for final review before submission
02/06/2023	0v4	Andrew Smith (ELIXIR Hub)	MB comments addressed
05/07/2023	1v0	Nikki Coutts (ELIXIR Hub)	Final version to be uploaded into EC Portal

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1. Executive Summary

The scope of the Deliverable is to update and release ELIXIR's Long-term Sustainability Plan (LTS Plan), which is now released as a public document, with a DOI (<https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1119412.1>) and lives on ELIXIR's F1000 gateway¹. Financial sustainability is a key topic for the successful operation of all research infrastructures and a clear, public document that describes the nature of the challenge and details the actions to be carried out to address those is crucial. ELIXIR has had a Long-term Sustainability Plan since 2019, and it is periodically updated and refreshed, taking into account new challenges and opportunities, and the completion of time-specific actions.

The aim of ELIXIR's Long-term Sustainability Plan is to set out short and long-term actions in order to support the sustainability of ELIXIR's activities, particularly ELIXIR Nodes and the services they run. There are over 400 services run by ELIXIR Nodes and this plan is not intended to act as or replace the need for those services to develop their own sustainability planning. Rather, the document focuses on high-level activities that can best support the long-term sustainability of ELIXIR as a whole, i.e. its capacity to maintain its activities over the long term.

The essential purpose and scope of the LTS Plan has not changed in this update: the scope is focussed on ELIXIR overall, not simply the sustainability of the CONVERGE project outputs, even though the Deliverable is carried out through the CONVERGE project. This is because INFRADEV-3, the topic through which ELIXIR-CONVERGE was funded, is there to support the

¹ <https://f1000research.com/documents/12-534>

overall operation of research infrastructures. Therefore the scope of the LTS Plan is ELIXIR overall. Similarly, the LTS Plan remains focussed on financial sustainability, rather than environmental sustainability. Indeed, the major change to the LTS Plan since the previous version has been to restructure the document and actions and to bring them in-line with the recommendations made by the European Commission and ESFRI on Long-term Sustainability of Research Infrastructures.

Whilst the Deliverable is delayed from the original planned date, work undertaken within ELIXIR in already implementing the actions contained within the LTS Plan has progressed as planned and has indeed remained a higher priority than publishing the final document. For example, now activates focussed on the Sustainability of Nodes through the acquisition of national funding via local roadmaps, and a workshop to bring together ELIXIR partners running services to discuss business models have been prioritised ahead of publishing the LTS plan, as this has a greater impact on ELIXIR overall.

2. Contribution toward project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

Objective no. / Key Result no. Description	Contributed to:
Objective 1: Develop a sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support by leveraging national capabilities (WP1, WP5)	
Key Result 1.1: Established European expert network of data stewards that connect national data centres and similar infrastructures and drive the development of interoperable solutions following international best practice, including national interpretations of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	No
Key Result 1.2: Development of joint guidelines and common toolkit that are adopted into funder recommendations, with support available nationally and in local languages	No
Key Result 1.3: The catalogue of successful national business models incorporated into national strategies	No
Key Result 1.4: The developed “sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support” is adopted into national ELIXIR Node	No

Objective 2: Strengthen Europe’s data management capacity through a comprehensive training programme delivered throughout the European Research Area (WP2, WP6)	
Key Result 2.1: A comprehensive ELIXIR Training and Capacity building programme in Data Management, directed at both data managers and ELIXIR users, and connected to the national training programmes in Data Management in the ELIXIR Nodes and prospective ELIXIR Member countries.	No
Key Result 2.2: Development of a collective group of trainers that support scalable deployment of Data Management training across ELIXIR Nodes.	No
Key Result 2.3: A substantial cohort of data managers, Node coordinators and researchers with specific data management skills, business planning and knowledge of transnational operations across the ELIXIR Nodes	No
Objective 3: Align national data management standards and services through a sustainable, scalable and cost-effective data management toolkit (WP2, WP3, WP5)	
Key Result 3.1: Assemble a full-stack harmonised common toolkit comprising all aspects of data management: from data capture, annotation, and sharing; to integration with analysis platforms and making the data publicly available according to international standards.	No
Key Result 3.2: Provide exemplar toolkit configurations for prioritised demonstrators to serve as templates for future use.	No
Key Result 3.3: Establish national capacity in using as well as updating, extending and sustaining the toolkit across the ERA.	No
Key Result 3.4: Enable ‘FAIR at source’ practice for data generation, and analytical process pipeline implementation by flexible deployment of the toolkit in national operations	No
Objective 4: Align national investments to drive local impact and global influence of ELIXIR (WP4,WP6)	
Key Result 4.1: Development of a Node Impact Assessment Toolkit based on RI-PATHS methodology.	No
Key Result 4.2: Adoption of Impact assessment in ELIXIR Nodes, supported by Node coordinators network and feedback on applicability from dialogues with national funders.	Yes
Key Result 4.3: Creation of national public-private partnerships and industry outreach where open life-science data and services stimulate local bioeconomy	Yes
Key Result 4.4: Growth in reach, impact and engagement of stakeholder communication assessed by established ELIXIR Communications metrics	No

<p>Key Result 4.5: Initiating and advancing discussions on Membership (EU and international) or strategic partnerships (international countries) following ELIXIR-CONVERGE workshops.</p>	<p>Yes</p>
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3. Introduction

The scope of the LTS Plan is ELIXIR in its entirety. The actions contained in the strategy involve and will be carried out by representatives of the Hub and Nodes and therefore are based on the the distributed nature of ELIXIR as a research infrastructure. With 22 countries and over 240 institutes involved in ELIXIR, the LTS Plan is intentionally a high-level document that acts as a framework to give context to the various challenges faced by ELIXIR, and show clearly what is being done to

ELIXIR already has a LTS Plan², last released in 2019, which has provided the same purpose as the 2023 updated version/ existed as a public document.

4. Description of work accomplished

The work has been led and coordinated by the External Relations team in the ELIXIR Hub, which is part-funded through the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project. Input, editing and review has been provided by the consortium through consultations carried out during 2022, and in the review of this Deliverable report. The LTS Plan is a public document and will be read and used by other research infrastructures seeking to adopt best practice from ELIXIR. But as ELIXIR’s overarching LTS Plan, contributions to the document have come from partners funded within ELIXIR-CONVERGE, with the document being open for input from partners in ELIXIR that are also not funded through CONVERGE, rather than from external stakeholders. However, the European Commission and ESFRI recommendations on long-term sustainability of research infrastructures.

The work is carried out within WP4 of ELIXIR-CONVERGE, but the document was open for drafting and input from all other Work Packages. The visibility of the work was kept high through updates during ELIXIR Programme meetings, which give a platform for updates from all CONVERGE Work Packages, as well as ELIXIR’s internal mailing lists reaching 800 internal ELIXIR partners.

The LTS Plan introduced ELIXIR and its funding model, which is shown graphically in Figure 1.

² <https://f1000research.com/documents/8-1642>

Figure 1. Showing ELIXIR is funded via a range of mostly public sources.

In addition to summarising the funding model of ELIXIR, the LTS Plan also details why bioinformatics services act as a public good. Given that ELIXIR is almost entirely funded through public funding, and that ELIXIR Nodes provide access to the majority of their resources for free (with the exception of computing facilities), it is imperative to describe why public funding for free access is so beneficial for the life science community. As the LTS Plan is read by stakeholders including funders, this section is important to remind them of why the publicly-funded model is indeed valuable.

The updated LTS Plan is structured around the following 7 ESFRI recommendations:

1. **Establish and maintain excellence** through the entire lifecycle of RIs by all appropriate means, by securing adequate framework conditions, and by opening the RIs up to the world,
2. **Ensure that research infrastructures have the right people in the right place at the right time**, by strengthening and harmonising national research and educational systems to make sure that all essential skills are available,
3. **Harmonise and integrate a vision for convergent operation of research infrastructures and e-Infrastructures** in Europe to ensure cost-effective service provision to the user communities,
4. **Fully exploit the potential of research infrastructures as innovation hubs** by incorporating strategies for their development into national and European innovation policies,
5. **Set up effective means of determining the economic and wider social value of research infrastructures** and incorporate these benefits into science-policy-society dialogues,

6. *Establish adequate framework conditions for **effective governance and sustainable long-term funding for research infrastructures** at every stage in their lifecycle, together with effective management,*
7. *Foster broader **coordination at National and European levels**, when designing processes for planning and supporting national and pan European RIs and so enhance their strategic value.*

Within each of these Recommendations, we list a table showing the actions that are currently or will be carried out in order to address that Recommendation. The Action is carried out by a representative(s) of ELIXIR, and the Notes section gives more context to how and when this will happen.

Example of Actions of relevance to Recommendation 1: ‘Establish and maintain excellence’.

Action	Notes
Develop and maintain benchmarks of quality and excellence in ELIXIR resources such as Core Data Resources (CDRs), ELIXIR Deposition Databases (EDDs) and Recommended Interoperability Resources (RIRs)	Sustainability work on CDRs taken forward by ELIXIR’s engagement in the Global Biodata Coalition.

5. Results

As a high-level strategy, the LTS Plan itself does not achieve visible results in the same way that a web-based resource can demonstrate new users or a social media account can demonstrate numbers of followers. However, the activities that are described within the LTS Plan, and thus prioritised for action/coordination by the ELIXIR External Relations team, have led to important results for ELIXIR already.

As shown in the LTS Plan, the ELIXIR Budget is funded through participating countries, so working towards expanding the Membership of ELIXIR has been a priority of WP4 activities:

- Austria has joined ELIXIR as an Observer³
- Croatia has applied to become a Member of ELIXIR
- Pathways to Membership have been developed for Poland, Romania, Slovakia and Latvia

In addition, the acquisition of funding, at the EU and national level, to support the operation of ELIXIR services and the coordination of ELIXIR Nodes has been prioritised and resulted in numerous successes. New EU projects have been awarded to ELIXIR⁴ including:

³ <https://elixir-europe.org/news/austria-joins>

⁴ <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/how-funded/eu-projects>

- Genomics Data Infrastructure
- BY-COVID
- Biodiversity Genome Europe (BGE)
- AgroServ
- Prophet
- CanSERV
- EOSC4Cancer
- Pathos
- EUCAIM

In addition, proposals to Horizon Europe have been prepared and submitted to the Calls for Proposals with 2023 deadlines, and whilst the outcome is currently unknown it can be expected that some will be funded.

Workshops on the topic of financial sustainability and business models around ELIXIR services have been organised in order to share best practice between ELIXIR members on this topic. A workshop during the ELIXIR All Hands meeting in 2023 will focus on exchanging best practice on the acquisition by ELIXIR Nodes of national funding.

6. Conclusions

The LTS Plan sets out the high-level activities that are being taken across ELIXIR overall to support sustainability, in particular the financial sustainability of ELIXIR services and national Nodes. The Actions described in the LTS Plan are structured against the recommendations of the European Commission and ESFRI on the sustainability of research infrastructures. The LTS Plan acts as a public document, a reference point to describe to funders and stakeholders the key challenges facing ELIXIR, and what coordinated activities are taking place across ELIXIR to try and address these.

7. Impact

As described in Section 5. Results, the LTS Plan itself is a high-level document that describes a set of activities that will be carried out by partners across ELIXIR - the impact achieved is through the implementation of those activities described in the document, as they will help to ensure ELIXIR is on the most sustainable footing.

In terms of the impact of the Plan itself, its predecessor⁵ published in 2019 has been downloaded almost 200 times and viewed almost 800 times (to date), suggesting a wide reach. Many of the activities described in the 2019 and 2023 LTS Plans target policy stakeholders, such as policy-makers and funders - ELIXIR's policy impact is significant and is being monitored through a

⁵ <https://f1000research.com/documents/8-1642>

public-facing indicator, available on our website⁶ (Figure 2). Of note, ELIXIR and its resources are mentioned in funders’ guide for grantees, as a direct result of activities described in the LTS Plans (Figure 3).

Outcomes of our efforts to shape policy

In parallel and as proxy for ELIXIR’s public value, we track mentions of ELIXIR, its projects, resources and key achievements, in policy documents, reports, guides for grantees, funding calls, etc. Our manual tracking is complemented by the Overton database, the world’s largest searchable index of policy documents, guidelines, think tank publications and working papers. We are proud that funding bodies increasingly mention and even recommend ELIXIR resources in their Open Science policies and guides for grantees. Access the full visualisations in [tableau](#).

Figure 2. ELIXIR’s policy impact, fostered by the many activities described in the LTS Plan, as shown on ELIXIR’s impact dashboard (<https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/impact/engagement>).

⁶ <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/impact/engagement>

Figure 3. ELIXIR was mentioned in funders’ guides for grantees during the project’s lifespan, as a direct result of engagement activities.

8. Next Steps

The updated LTS Plan is a public document, and lives in the ELIXIR F1000Res gateway, along with other ELIXIR policy documents. It will act as a resource that will show ELIXIR partners, and funders, what activities are taking place. When required, updates will be presented at relevant governance committees such as the ELIXIR Board or Head of Nodes meetings. It will be shared with those groups in ELIXIR that are likely to find it useful, such as ELIXIR Node Coordinators and Heads of Nodes. It will be referenced and used in future submissions to ESFRI and will be shared with colleagues involved in developing sustainability plans for other research infrastructures. If opportunities present themselves, we will present ELIXIR’s LTS Plan during talks at ESFRI conferences and other fora that bring together funders and policy-makers.

9. Deviation from Description of Action

The activities described in the proposal have been carried out, so there has been no deviation in activity. There has, however, been a delay to the publication of the LTS from that originally foreseen. This delay of 9 months has enabled ELIXIR to focus on implementing many of the activities that are described in the LTS Plan, such as acquiring new EU funding, supporting Nodes with the acquisition of national funding and expanding the Membership of ELIXIR to new countries. For example, in the time between the original publication date and the actual release, work has been done to support the path towards Membership of ELIXIR by several countries

including Austria and Croatia. This has had a higher impact on ELIXIR than a publication of the LTS Plan in September 2022 would have had.

